

AI-native architecture for 6G networks and services with model dependencies

Nassima Toumi

Networks

TNO

The Hague, The Netherlands

nassima.toumi@tno.nl

Toni Dimitrovski

Networks

TNO

The Hague, The Netherlands

toni.dimitrovski@tno.nl

Abstract—Next generation networks and services increasingly rely on AI/ML methods to integrate intelligence in the decision making process with the introduction of MLOps pipelines for automating orchestration and lifecycle management. Further, Digital Twinning is viewed as a key enabling technology for 6G networks due to its foreseen benefits in network management optimization by providing a digital replica of the network. However, further work is required for an AI-native 6G architecture that fully integrates AI/ML into network and service management. Indeed, the use of Digital Twins and Transfer Learning leads to dependencies between models, which ought to be taken into account during their lifecycle management. Hence, the work described in this paper provides a framework for enabling an AI-native network architecture which supports the handling of AI/ML model interdependencies and relationships in network and service management and orchestration.

Index Terms—6G, AI, Digital Twin, MANO

I. INTRODUCTION

5G and beyond networks and services rely on orchestration and management frameworks and procedures to automate service lifecycle management and ensure the satisfaction of strict performance requirements. To support this automation, different solutions have been proposed in the literature for intelligent (e.g. Zero-Touch) lifecycle management, where AI/ML models are used for event prediction, KPI prediction and orchestration decision-making. A more specific example is the use of Digital Twins to emulate the network environment behaviour for safe AI/ML training or synthetic data generation [1], [2].

However, to ensure the efficiency of service orchestration, these AI/ML models also require a specific Control Loop (CL) for managing their lifecycle in an automated manner. Indeed, as the environment is dynamic (e.g. changes in traffic, user behaviour, infrastructure changes), the performance of trained AI/ML models might drop if their training dataset did not contain relevant representative features, or if it is not up to date and is therefore not a good general representation of the environment anymore. Consequently, different MLOps solutions have been proposed to monitor, re-train and re-deploy AI/ML models in an automated manner. However, the proposed solutions only consider individual models, and do not consider relationships and dependencies between different models, as well as between the models and data used to

train them. Indeed, there are multiple cases where AI/ML models are trained based on other models such as Transfer Learning (TL), Continual Learning, or Digital Twins (DT) for generating synthetic training data or providing a safe training environment. In these scenarios, the dependency aspect is important to consider since a performance degradation for the base model might be an indicator of a future degradation for dependent models and vice versa. Similarly, if the performance of a model drops due to the aforementioned issue, other models that have been trained using the same dataset might also require a proactive update.

To this end, the present paper provides a framework for enabling AI-native architectures for next generation mobile networks that comprises an end-to-end AI/ML model control loop for automated data collection and model (re-)training, (re-) deployment, and monitoring while considering different model and data dependencies. The proposed solution introduces a repository function which stores dependencies and relationships between different models, and between models and data sources. Using those dependencies, the proposed model orchestration framework can determine the models and/or data sources that have direct or indirect dependencies with the degraded model, and perform the appropriate mitigation actions.

This paper is organized as follows: Section II provides an overview on the state of the art in the literature and 3GPP standards. Section III describes the proposed solution, with an example use case of inter-CL dependencies, the proposed architecture and its functional components, as well as the workflows for AI/ML model training and post-deployment lifecycle management. Session IV discusses the provided solution, while Session V concludes the paper.

II. STATE OF THE ART

A. Standards

The 3GPP standards define the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) function in the 5G architecture which is in charge of training AI/ML models based on data collected from different functions in the architecture, and providing data analytics [3]. The NWDAF is composed of two logical functions: The Analytics Logical Function (AnLF) which is in charge of performing inference and exposing analytics/predictions, and

the Model Training Logical Function (MTLF) which trains ML models and provides them to the AnLF. Data collection can be performed by a separate function, the Data Collection Coordination Function (DCCF), and the collected data and the produced analytics can be stored in the Analytics Data Repository Function (ADRF) for future use by any NF in the 5G core. In the latest release of 5G system standards, a mechanism for AI/ML model performance monitoring and improvement has been introduced which allows the AnLF to continuously monitor model performance and to trigger a model update process in the MTLF when detecting model degradation. The AI/ML model information has also been enhanced to include details on the data that has been used to train each AI/ML model such as the data sources, statistical metrics (e.g. number of input values, mean, standard deviation...), and information on the time and duration of data collection. However, it should be noted that pre-trained AI/ML model storage and provisioning to the NWDAF is considered out of scope.

B. MLOps and Closed Control Loops

On the other hand, to automate AI/ML model training and deployment, AI-based automated Closed Control Loops (CCLs) have been proposed in the literature. In IMT 2020, the ITU provides a recommendation [4] for Machine Learning usage in future networks, which includes multiple high-level requirements, as well as an architectural framework that features an ML sandbox subsystem with its own ML pipeline. The ML sandbox allows model training, testing and evaluation pre-deployment, and uses data generated from simulated underlay networks to augment training data. The work in [5] proposes an architecture for AI-assisted End-to-End multi-domain CCLs for network orchestration that comprise four main stages: Monitoring, Analysis, Decision, and Execution. In this work, the CCLs of the cloud, transport, edge and RAN domain CCLs interact with a centralized End-to-End CCL to enable cross-domain collaborative resource orchestration. The architecture is evaluated on multiple use case scenarios, where one scenario uses a DT of the transport network in an offline workflow to generate data on faulty behavior and train the ML model accordingly. Chatzieleftheriou et al. [6] elaborate a unified framework and a set of orchestration procedures to support the deployment of Network Intelligence Services in different network layers of the 6G networks. The framework implements AI/ML model lifecycle management, conflict resolution, and knowledge sharing within and between Network Intelligence Services. To support AI/ML lifecycle management, dedicated MLOps pipelines are implemented for data processing and model training, testing, monitoring, and re-training if deemed necessary. Similarly, the authors of [7] develop an AI-native system architecture for integrating MLOps, Edge Computing and extreme edge resources into 6G network systems to enable Edge Intelligence and Edge AI. To this end, the architecture includes distributed components that support MLOps and monitoring pipelines for Zero-Touch service, data and AI/ML model lifecycle management. The

Hexa-X project [8] also identifies a set of enabling AIaaS functions for AI model training, monitoring, and storage and provides different frameworks for AIaaS that expose unified APIs for AIaaS functions and include MLOps workflows and procedures for automated model deployment and lifecycle management. However, the proposed automated AI/ML orchestration loops and frameworks in the cited works do not consider the dependencies between multiple AI/ML models, and between AI/ML models and the datasets or Digital Twins that have been used to train them. Note that a Digital Twin may also be an AI/ML model, but in this case we distinguish between a model of a physical entity named a Digital Twin, and other AI/ML models, for example a predictive model of a KPI or a policy learned with Reinforcement Learning. The solution provided by the present paper bridges this gap by managing AI/ML model dependencies and using them for triggering model management operations within and across control loops.

III. SOLUTION DESCRIPTION

A. Inter-Control Loop dependencies

Fig. 1. Model dependency use case example

As introduced earlier, the solution described in this paper enables inter-CL event trigger based on the dependencies between the models. Figure 1 illustrates an example use case, where AI/ML models in an AI-Native architecture are used to perform policy control and user plane forwarding in the network infrastructure, as well as a Digital Twin of the environment to provide training data for the models. The AI/ML models and the Digital Twin are inter-dependent. Namely, Model 1 has been trained with Transfer Learning using the base Model 2. In turn, that base model has been trained based on input from the DT. Finally, additional to Model 2, the DT has been employed to generate part of the dataset used as input for the training of Models 3 and 4 with varying proportions (15 and 50% respectively).

In this example, the models and DT have been trained based on the network state including the type of users. Thus, as shown in the figure, the addition of new type(s) of users to the network creates a significant change in the state of environment that was not captured by the Digital Twin, and causes a

Fig. 2. Inter-Control Loop dependencies

performance degradation in Model 2. This performance degradation can then affect additional models such as Model 1 as the new type(s) of users move to different locations. Instead of updating each model in a reactive manner after the degradation has been observed, the model dependency relationships can be leveraged to minimize performance degradation by triggering updates in dependent models in a proactive manner.

Figure 2 depicts the workflow for such mechanism, where 5 MLOps CLs perform the management of the AI/ML models and the Digital Twin. When performance degradation is observed for the Model 2, the CL management determines that the appropriate mitigation action is to update the model. However, the cause of degradation for the model is determined to be due to the DT in CL5 being no longer accurate. Thus, before updating the Model 2, CL5 needs to trigger an update operation for its DT. Once the DT has been updated, a notification is sent to the CLs of all dependent models, namely, CLs 2, 3 and 4. Upon receiving the notification, CL2 triggers a model update based on the newly generated DT. Additionally, due to the TL dependency, this update in CL2 triggers an action in CL1 to also update its model. Finally, based on the proportion of the input from the DT and in accordance with pre-configured policies or optimized decision logic, CLs 3 and 4 may trigger an update of their respective models based on input from the updated Digital Twin.

B. Description of the architectural framework

As shown in Figure 3, the proposed solution provides an enhanced framework that employs multiple (optionally distributed) functions to support MLOps control loops for AI/ML model orchestration:

- **AI/ML model training:** This function performs model training similar to the MTLF in 3GPP. It retrieves the dataset to be used as input to perform AI/ML model training and validation from the repository function. If the new model training relies on another model (e.g. in case of Transfer Learning or Continual Learning), the

function retrieves the base model from the repository as well. Additionally, this function may use a sandbox environment including Digital Twins (to be retrieved from the repository) to enable a safe AI/ML model training and validation.

- **AI/ML model inference agent:** This function corresponds to the AnLF in 3GPP, it performs inference using the model trained by the AI/ML model training function and retrieved from the model repository. The agent also provides model performance reports to the model monitoring function.
- **AI/ML model monitoring:** This function is responsible for collecting and aggregating different performance reports from the AI/ML model inference agents, and to determine the model's average accuracy across agents. The function then sends alerts to the AI/ML orchestration function when model performance drops below a certain threshold. It may also use the output of other AI/ML model inference agents to make predictions on events and metrics affecting model performance such as user mobility or network load, and triggers alarms in advance to allow preventive measures. Further, the monitoring function is able to identify additional instances that might be affected by the detected drop in the future based on context information, and provide this additional information in the alert (e.g. in case the behavior of a group of users accessing a service changes which causes a performance degradation for one model instance, and those users are expected to move towards an area covered by another model instance).
- **Data collection/generation function:** This function performs data collection similar to the DCCF in 3GPP, as well as pre-processing prior to storage. It interfaces with different data sources in the network to collect data on demand, or periodically to maintain data accuracy and freshness (e.g. for keeping Digital Twins up to date). Additionally, this function can use an inference agent to

Fig. 3. AI-Native architecture for efficient AI/ML model orchestration

deploy a Digital Twin from the repository to generate synthetic data for creating or augmenting a dataset. The collected data is pre-processed and stored in the repository, and can also be provided to the AI/ML model orchestration function (e.g. to trigger model updates in case of changes in the environment).

- **Data and model repository:** Similar to the ADRF in 3GPP, this repository serves to store and provide AI/ML models, Digital Twins, datasets and their related metadata. Namely, the following information elements are stored by the repository:
 - General metadata such as the ID and version, selection filters or tags (that may help filter and select the appropriate dataset, Digital Twin or model) such as the service or application type, or provided output (e.g. UE mobility, network load, service QoS...). The framework uses a unified specification in the selection filter or tag metadata. This allows the selection of datasets and DTs for training, base models of interest in case of TL, or for deploying a model for a new service.
 - Algorithm and accuracy information for the AI/ML models and DTs.
 - For datasets, additional metadata includes data source(s), volume, distribution, data collection/generation time and duration. Datasets can also include synthetic data that has been generated by Digital Twins.
 - Additionally, the repository maintains information on the dependency relationships between the different AI/ML models, Digital Twins and datasets, which helps propagate mitigation actions as described in the previous subsection.
- **AI/ML model orchestration:** This function is the main

decision component of the AI-Native framework. Similar to a service orchestrator, it manages the lifecycle of the model and its different versions by collecting monitoring data, making decisions and communicating with the other functions to trigger different operations with the aim of maintaining model performance in an automated manner. It may also use the output of other AI/ML model inference agents in its decision making to determine the appropriate orchestration actions.

- **AI/ML exposure function:** This function provides a unified interface or endpoint for the AI/ML model consumer to request the training and deployment of new models, or to update pre-deployed models. To facilitate request processing, it exposes selection filter information related to the available AI/ML models and Digital Twins that are stored in the repository function. The requests are forwarded to the AI/ML model orchestration function for further processing.

C. Workflow description

1) *AI Model training and exposure:* Figure 4 illustrates the workflow of the initial AI/ML model training and deployment in the proposed AI native architecture. Upon receiving a request for a new AI/ML model (e.g. request to provide models for a new service deployment) via the exposure function, the AI/ML model orchestrator identifies the type of AI/ML model to satisfy the request by querying the repository function, and initiates the AI/ML model training function to train a new model if there is no pre-trained model already available. To this end, the AI/ML model orchestration function might trigger new data collection or synthetic data generation beforehand if additional data is needed. Then the AI/ML model orchestrator sends a request to the AI/ML model training function comprising information on the required model, a reference to the training dataset to be retrieved from the repository, and

Fig. 4. AI model deployment workflow

optionally the ID and version of a base model to use for the training in case of TL or Continual Learning, or the ID of a DT if required for training the model. The AI/ML model training function then trains the model accordingly and stores it in the repository. Afterwards, the AI/ML model orchestrator determines the set of inference agents to deploy the model and provides the ID of the newly generated model to the set of identified inference agents so that they can retrieve it from the repository. Finally, the AI/ML model orchestrator instructs the AI/ML model monitoring function to start monitoring the deployed model. The monitoring function then subscribes to inference results for the model for all AI/ML model inference agents.

2) *Post-deployment lifecycle management*: Figure 5 shows the workflow of the post-deployment lifecycle management operations of an AI/ML model. Once the model has been deployed on the inference function(s), the AI/ML model monitoring function collects and aggregates periodical performance reports from the inference function(s), and sends an alert to the AI/ML model orchestrator if model performance drop is observed or predicted for one or multiple model instances. Upon reception of the alert, the orchestrator identifies the cause and scope of the degradation such as changes in the network or service behavior. The appropriate mitigation action is determined based to this information according to policies or decision optimization logic in the AI/ML model orchestrator, which is out of the scope of the present paper. Mitigation actions can include deploying another previously trained version of the model, re-training a new model with new data

from new sources if necessary, optimizing the model training process by re-using existing models for TL or Continual Learning to extend the AI/ML model with new data while preserving previously learned knowledge. Further, based on the cause of the degradation and the mitigation action, the orchestrator determines the possible impact on other inference instances of the model as well as other models. To do so, it may query the repository function to retrieve possible dependencies and relationships between the model and other models or data sources. Using those dependencies, the AI/ML orchestrator can determine the models and data sources that have direct or indirect dependencies with the degraded model. Then, if applicable, the orchestrator determines the appropriate mitigation action such as proactive AI/ML model update or model replacement for the identified instances depending on the degree of dependency. The mitigation actions are then applied for each model, DT or data in the required order of dependency. The mitigation actions might be propagated recursively over multiple iterations in case of more complex cases with extended chains of dependencies as illustrated in the use case example described in Section III-A.

IV. DISCUSSION

The solution developed in this work will enhance support for next generations network and service capabilities by maintaining the performance of AI/ML models that can be used in the network system (e.g. Zero-Touch network and service orchestration) and the services deployed on it. The architecture and workflows described in this paper enable an improved au-

Fig. 5. AI model post-deployment lifecycle management workflow

tomated ML model lifecycle management by considering, for each model, different dependencies with other models, Digital Twins and datasets. In doing so, some model degradations can be predicted in advance and proactively mitigated based on events in the CLs of other dependent models or datasets. Thus, response time to AI/ML model performance degradation can be reduced, and AI/ML model overall performance can be maintained over its lifecycle. Further, the model training time can be reduced by re-using available pre-trained models and datasets whenever possible.

However, to keep track of the model and data dependencies, additional metadata needs to be collected, stored and maintained about each model, Digital Twin and dataset that is managed within the framework. Managing these dependencies and relationships also requires a unified naming or tagging system to facilitate identifying the model, DT, dataset or data source which is most suitable for satisfying a given demand. Additionally, these dependencies lead to more complex CL management and interactions, where events in a CL can trigger actions in other CLs, with possible recursive effects in multiple dependent CLs over multiple iterations.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper provides a framework and set of workflows for AI-native next generation network and services, by adding the missing aspect of data-algorithm-model dependencies. The proposed framework and workflows also helps further automate AI/ML model lifecycle management by providing mechanisms allowing individual CLs to communicate and trigger events in other CLs based on the dependencies between the models and data. The described solution also improves ML lifecycle management with the early prediction, detection and prevention of ML model performance degradation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been partially funded by the EC through the SNS JU Hexa-X-II project under grant agreement No. 101095759.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Pérez-Valero, A. Virdis, A. G. Sánchez, C. Ntogkas, P. Serrano, G. Landi, S. Kukliński, C. Morin, I. L. Pavón, and B. Sayadi, "AI-driven orchestration for 6g networking: the hexa-x vision," in *2022 IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps)*, 2022, pp. 1335–1340.
- [2] A. Masaracchia, V. Sharma, B. Canberk, O. A. Dobre, and T. Q. Duong, "Digital twin for 6g: Taxonomy, research challenges, and the road ahead," *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 3, pp. 2137–2150, 2022.
- [3] 3GPP, "Architecture enhancements for 5G System (5GS) to support network data analytics services," 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), Technical Specification (TS) 23.288, 09 2023, version 18.3.0.
- [4] ITU-T, "Architectural framework for machine learning in future networks including IMT-2020," International Telecommunication Union, Recommendation Y.3172, 2019.
- [5] N. F. S. de Sousa, M. T. Islam, R. U. Mustafa, D. A. L. Perez, C. E. Rothenberg, and P. H. Gomes, "Machine learning-assisted closed-control loops for beyond 5g multi-domain zero-touch networks," *Journal of Network and Systems Management*, vol. 30, no. 3, p. 46, Apr 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10922-022-09651-x>
- [6] L. E. Chatzieftheriou, M. Gramaglia, M. Camelo, A. Garcia-Saavedra, E. Kosmatos, M. Gucciardo, P. Soto, G. Iosifidis, L. Fuentes, G. Garcia-Aviles, A. Lutu, G. Baldoni, and M. Fiore, "Orchestration procedures for the network intelligence stratum in 6g networks," in *2023 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, 2023, pp. 347–352.
- [7] N. Psaromanolakis, V. Theodorou, D. Laskaratos, I. Kalogeropoulos, M.-E. Vrontzou, E. Zarogianni, and G. Samaras, "Mlops meets edge computing: an edge platform with embedded intelligence towards 6g systems," in *2023 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, 2023, pp. 496–501.
- [8] Hexa-X, "Deliverable D5.2: Analysis of 6G architectural enablers applicability and initial technological solutions," 2023, project deliverable.